

FATIGUE DAMAGES OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER SERVICE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

A stiffness degradation model, which has been proved to be capable of estimating the cumulative damages in composite laminates due to constant amplitude fatigue loading, is used to predict the fatigue damage of composite laminates under service loading. The real service loading sequence is taken from the upper surface of the horizontal tail of a fighter aircraft and is random in nature. In order to employ the stiffness degradation model, the service loading is divided into 20 small loading blocks. Each loading block contains more or less similar loading cycles and, hence, possesses similar probabilistic characteristics. Then, the residual stiffness of composite laminate is predicted by employing the stiffness degradation model based on the counting of small loading blocks. Experiments were performed on $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2s}$ graphite/epoxy laminates to generate statistically meaningful data for verifying the stiffness reduction model. Comparisons between the theoretical predictions and experimental results are shown to be good.

Keywords: Fatigue, Stiffness deradation, Fatigue damage, Service loading

1. INTRODUCTION

While the advanced composite materials attract increasing application on the aircraft industry and the design of aircraft is toward the concept of damage tolerance, it requires a methodology to characterize the fatigue damages of composite materials before it can be used with confidence. In order to accomplish this purpose, there have been many research works on this subject and various approaches have been proposed. Mechanistic approach[1] is difficult to explain the damages of composites since they involve many damage mechanisms such as matrix crackings, fiber breakages, fiber-matrix debonding and delaminations due to fatigue. Furthermore, some of these damage mechanisms could interact simultaneously.

Many investigations illustrate that the fatigue damages in composites can be evaluated by measuring the change of the material properties, e.g., the stiffness or strength. Extensive research efforts have been conducted to investigate the degradation of residual strength under fatigue loading. Many strength degradation models have also been proposed[2-4] and the

residual strength during fatigue cycling was predicted based on those models. Since the measurement of the residual strength of composite involves the destructive of the test specimen, a fatigue damage model based on the residual strength may not be suitable for predicting and tracking of fatigue damages. Salkind *et al.* [5] suggested the utilization the stiffness change in composites as a damage parameter, since the stiffness reduces accordingly during fatigue cycling. Later, many researchers studied the relationship between damage modes and the reduction of residual stiffness of composite materials[6-8]. Many stiffness degradation models for fatigue were proposed[9-13] since then. Because the residual stiffness can be measured nondestructively, a stiffness-based degradation model may be more suitable to track and predict the fatigue damages in composites during its service.

Recently Yang *et al.* [12] developed a stiffness degradation model which has been used successfully to predict the residual stiffness for the fiber dominated composite laminates under constant amplitude tension-tension fatigue loading. Its predictive ability has also been verified by experiments. Later, Yang *et al.* [13] modified the aforementioned stiffness degradation model to matrix dominated composite laminates which have nonlinear stress-strain relationship and involve considerable permanent plastic deformation during fatigue cycling. To circumvent this difficulty, they used the fatigue modulus [11] as a damage index in the modified stiffness degradation model. Their predictions were also verified by experiments.

All the aforementioned research efforts have been emphasized on the fatigue of composites under constant amplitude fatigue loading. However, service loading on aircraft structures is random in nature, the fatigue data of composites obtained under constant amplitude fatigue cycling may not be adequate for design purposes. In addition, fatigue analysis of composites subjected to random service loading is a very complicated process, though it can be simplified by the use of spectrum loading. Recently, many researchers have investigated the fatigue behavior of composites by using spectrum loadings[4,14-16]. However, the load sequence has significant effect[3] on the fatigue damage and life of composite laminates.

The purpose of this study is to employ the stiffness degradation model proposed by Yang *et al.*[12] to study the fatigue behavior of composite laminates under service loading. A real cyclic loading history taken from the surface of the horizontal stabilizer of a fighter aircraft comprises about a total of 19440 load cycles which were collected from 500 flight hours or 596 flights. This real load history was divided into 20 similar small blocks. Then, the statistical distribution of the residual stiffness of composites is predicted at any arbitrary small loading block using the aforementioned stiffness degradation model. Through tracking the stiffness reduction of a specific specimen, the residual stiffness at subsequent small loading blocks of that specimen is also predicted by using either the regression analysis or Bayesian statistical approach. Experiments were performed on $[0^\circ/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]_2$ graphite/epoxy laminates to generate statistically meaningful data for verifying the stiffness reduction model. Comparisons between the theoretical predictions and experimental results are shown to be good.

2. RESIDUAL STIFFNESS DEGRADATION MODEL

Suppose the service loading is expressed as a repetition of some small fundamental loading block, the stiffness degradation model can be used to estimate the residual stiffness of composites at any arbitrary small loading block. In such case, the residual stiffness is predicted using the stiffness degradation model based on counting of small loading blocks instead of loading cycles.

Similar to constant amplitude fatigue, the residual stiffness for fiber dominated composite laminate in service loading is expressed as [12]:

$$E(n) = E(0)(1 - Qn^v). \quad (1)$$

in which $E(0)$ is the initial stiffness before loading applied, Q and v are parameters depending on the applied maximum stress level S , and n is the number of small loading blocks.

Experimental results indicate that parameters Q and v are linearly correlated and can be expressed as

$$Q = a_1 + a_2v \quad (2)$$

where a_1 and a_2 are parameters independent of the applied maximum stress level S . Experimental data further indicates that the parameter v is function of the maximum stress level, S , of the service loading and can be expressed as

$$v = a_3 + BS \quad (3)$$

where a_3 is a parameter, and B is a random variable. Substituting Eqs. (2) and (3) into Eq.(1) yields

$$E(n) = E(0) \left[1 - (d + a_2BS)n^{a_3+BS} \right] \quad (4)$$

where $d = a_1 + a_2a_3$. This equation represents the residual stiffness degradation model[12] for fiber dominated composites. It has to be pointed out again that the model is used on counting small loading blocks, which will be defined later, for service loading.

2.1 Statistical Distribution of Residual Stiffness

It is well known that the residual stiffness of composite laminates varies considerably from specimen to specimen. Such a statistical variability is represented by $E(0)$ and B in the residual stiffness degradation model given by Eq.(4). Experimental results indicate that $E(0)$ and B are statistically independent, and can be represented by lognormal and normal distributions, respectively. The distribution function of the residual stiffness, denoted by $F_{E(n)}(x) = P[E(n) \leq x]$, can be obtained from the transformation of Eq.(4) using the theorem of total probability,

$$F_{E(n)}(x) = \int_0^\infty F_{E(0)}[y(x, b)] f_B(b) db \quad (5)$$

where

$$y(x, b) = \frac{x}{\left[1 - (d + a_2bS)n^{a_3+bS} \right]}$$

where $f_B(b)$ are the probability density functions of B .

2.2 Prediction of Residual Stiffness for an Individual Specimen in Service

Two different methodologies i.e., the method of linear regression analysis and Bayesian statistical approach, suggested by Yang *et al.*[12] are used herein to predict the stiffness degradation of an individual specimen by utilizing the available service data. When base-line data are not available, linear regression analysis is employed to predict the residual stiffness of an

individual component using the measured service data alone. When the base-line data are also available, in addition to the service data, Bayesian approach is used to achieve the same task. These two approaches are described briefly in the following.

If base-line data are not available, the parameters Q and v in the residual stiffness degradation model, Eq.(1), are not known in advance. The residual stiffness at any arbitrary small loading cycle of an individual specimen is predicted by using the measured service data of that specimen alone, and can be expressed as

$$E(n) = E(0) \left[1 - \left(\frac{n}{n_k} \right)^{v(k)} \left(1 - \frac{E(n_k)}{E(0)} \right) \right]. \quad (6)$$

There is only one parameter $v(k)$ appearing in Eq.(6). This parameter can be estimated using the linear regression analysis. Once $v(k)$ is obtained, Eq.(6) can be used to predict the future residual stiffness $E(n_{k+1}), \dots, E(n_{k+m})$ at the n_{k+1} th, \dots, n_{k+m} th loading block. Detailed procedures of estimating $v(k)$ is given in Ref. 12.

If the base-line data are also available in addition to the measured service data, prediction of the residual stiffness for an individual component can also be made. In this case, the prior distribution of B is known from base-line data. After the service data of that specimen were measured, the posterior distribution of B can be obtained by the Bayesian approach. The residual stiffness degradation model for an individual specimen obtained by this method can be expressed as follows [12].

$$E(n) = E(0) \left[1 - (d + a_2 BS)n^{a_3 + BS} \right] + \eta \quad (7)$$

where η is the deviation of residual stiffness of that specific specimen from the mean of the entire population, it is a statistical variable, and can be assumed to be normally distributed with zero mean. Thus,

$$\sigma_\eta = \sigma_{E(0)}. \quad (8)$$

The future residual stiffness distribution for $n > n_k$ can be derived by using the total probability theorem

$$F_{E(n)}(z) = \int_0^\infty \Phi \left[\frac{z - \mu_n}{\sigma_\eta} \right] f'_B(b) db. \quad (9)$$

where

$$\mu_n = E(0) \left[1 - (d + a_2 bS)n^{a_3 + bS} \right]. \quad (10)$$

and $f'_B(b)$ is the posterior density function of B . The detailed derivation of Eq.(9) can be found in Ref. 12.

3. SERVICE FATIGUE LOADING

For the fatigue tests, a loading sequence corresponding to a critical point on the upper surface of the horizontal tail of a fighter aircraft is chosen as fatigue loading. This loading sequence comprises 19440 cycles which occur in 596 flights or 500 flight hours. Although this service loading sequence is random in nature, it consists only 98 segments whose stress amplitude and stress ratio differ with each other. Each of the segment consists of different numbers of identical loading cycles.

The stiffness degradation model can not be applied directly to predict fatigue damages of composite laminates under random service loading, since it is derived for constant amplitude fatigue loading and the residual stiffness is predicted based upon fatigue cycles. In order to circumvent this difficulty, total 19440 cycles of the service loading sequence is divided into 20 small loading blocks. Loading cycles in every segment are equally distributed to each of the small loading cycles. If the loading cycles in a segment is less than 20, these loading cycles are distributed randomly to the 20 small blocks. Thus, each small loading block obtained in such way possesses similar probabilistic characteristics. Assuming that this actual loading history can be modeled by repeating the original loading sequence, and hence, it can be considered as repeating these 20 small loading blocks. For these reasons, the fatigue behavior of composite laminates subjected to service loading can be evaluated based on the small loading blocks instead of loading cycles through the use of stiffness degradation model[12].

4. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The test specimens used in the experiments were made of graphite/epoxy manufactured by Fiberite company. It consisted of T300 graphite fiber and 976 epoxy resin. The lay-up was $[0^\circ/90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]_{2s}$ such that the strength of the laminates is controlled by the fiber properties. The nominal dimension of the specimens was 184 mm long, 38 mm wide. End taps were also used to prevent specimen from damaging by hydraulic grips of the testing machine. The taps were made of glass/epoxy laminates with thickness of 2 mm. They are bonded to the ends of the specimens with CIBA-GEIGY Araldite AV8 adhesives. During the fatigue tests, a set of specially designed compressive guiding plates was used to prevent from the laminate buckling, since there are high compressive loading dominated in the service loading. All tests were performed using an MTS 810 universal testing machine.

Twelve specimens were tested statically under tension to determine the ultimate strength at a cross head speed of 2.5 cm/s which would be close to the actual loading rate in fatigue tests. The average ultimate strength of the 20 specimens is 579.8 MPa with a standard deviation of 21.3 MPa. The mean initial stiffness $E(0)$ is 41.93 GPa with a standard deviation of 0.47 GPa. Another four specimens were tested statically under compression with the aide of a set of anti-buckling guiding plates. An average of compressive stress, 550.8 MPa, were reached before the specimens started to buckle. The mean compressive stiffness for the four specimens is almost same as the tensile stiffness(within the standard deviation). For this reason, the compressive strength of the laminate considered herein is assumed to be the same as the tensile strength. All the stress level used hereafter is referred to the ultimate mean tensile strength.

The fatigue tests were performed at a loading frequency of 10 Hz and at four different maximum compressive stress levels. The magnitude of the maximum compressive stress are 65, 70, 75, and 80 percent, respectively, of the ultimate tensile strength, corresponding to -376.7, -405.9, -434.9 and -463.8 MPa. Eleven specimens were tested at each applied stress level. Hence, a total of 44 specimens were tested. During fatigue tests, forces and displacements were measured at a specific loading cycle in preassigned small loading blocks. Then, the residual stiffness $E(n)$ is calculated from the measured test data.

5. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

The process of experimental verification is similar to that done in Ref. 12. Data sets obtained corresponding to the four stress levels are designated as data sets No.1, No.2, No.3, and No.4

respectively. In predicting the distribution of residual stiffness for any specific data set, the remained three data sets are considered as base-line data from which the model parameters in Eq.(5) are estimated. Then, Eq.(5) is employed to derive the theoretical distribution of the residual stiffness of that particular data set. The method of estimating the model parameters a_1, a_2, a_3 , and the mean values and the standard deviations, (μ_0, σ_0) , and (μ_B, σ_B) , of $\ln E(0)$, and B , respectively, are similar to those described in Ref. 12. A summary of these model parameters are listed in Table 1 for different base-line data sets.

The distribution of the residual stiffness will be predicted first to verify the validity of the proposed model. Predictions will be made for data set No. 2 using the base-line data sets Nos. 1,3, and 4 as shown in the second row of Table 1. The distribution of the residual stiffness at the 20th block for data set No. 2 is obtained and displayed in Fig. 1(a) as a solid curve. Also shown in the figure as solid circles are the experimental data for comparison. In a similar manner, predictions and experimental results for the distributions of the residual stiffness are made at the 200th loading blocks and shown in Fig. 1(b). It is observed from these figures that the theoretical predictions correlate well with the experimental results. For other data sets, i.e. data sets Nos. 1,3, and 4, the theoretical predictions and experimental results at different loading blocks were correlated equally well as those shown in Fig. 1. Due to space limitation, they are not presented here.

If the residual stiffness data of a specimen were measured up to n_k blocks, Eq. (6) can be used to predict the future residual stiffness of that specimen at subsequent small load blocks for $n \geq n_k$. The regression predictions of the residual stiffness for specimen F312 are shown as solid circles in Fig. 2(a-b) when the residual stiffness data are available up to (a) $n_k = 20$ blocks, (b) $n_k = 150$ blocks. The experimental data for this specimen are shown in the same figure as open circles for comparison.

If the base-line data for the residual stiffness degradation are also available in addition to the measured service data, Bayesian approach enables one to predict the statistical distribution of the residual stiffness for a particular specimen. The capability of the Bayesian approach is demonstrated in Fig. 3(a-b) using the same specimen as in regression analysis. The solid circles in Fig. 3 denote the predicted residual stiffness degradation based on the Bayesian approach, while the open circles represents for the test results. The two solid curves in Fig. 3 are the predicted 90% probability and 10% probability for the residual stiffness degradation behavior.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Fatigue damages in composite laminate subjected to service loading were investigated in this paper through monitoring of the reduction of its stiffness. In order to utilize the existing stiffness degradation model, which is valid for constant amplitude fatigue loading, to predict the residual stiffness of composite laminate under random service loading. The service loading is divided into 20 small loading blocks, each of which possesses similar probabilistic characteristics. Then, the residual stiffness of composite laminates is predicted using the stiffness degradation model based on counting of the number of the defined small loading blocks.

Experiments were performed on $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2s}$ graphite/epoxy laminates to generate statistically meaningful data for comparison with the theoretical predictions. Good correlations between experimental results and theoretical forecasting were found in this research.

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Data Set	a_1	a_2	a_3	μ_0	σ_0	μ_B	σ_B
No.2, 3, 4	0.06733	-0.2602	0.02446	3.7495	0.02426	.0002033	.00008265
No.1, 3, 4	0.06899	-0.2680	0.1154	3.7515	0.02591	.00001117	.00007684
No.1, 2, 4	0.07117	-0.2906	0.08553	3.7535	0.02121	.00007077	.00008815
No.1, 2, 3	0.07512	-0.3313	0.09878	3.7548	0.02541	.00002375	.00007911

Table 1 Model parameters for different base-line data set.

Fig. 1 Comparison between the prediction distribution of residual stiffness and experimental results at different loading blocks ($S = 405$ MPa). (a) $n_k = 20$ blocks; (b) $n_k = 200$ blocks.

Fig. 2 Comparison between predicted residual stiffness (regression analysis) and experimental results for specimen F312 ($S = 376.7$ MPa, $N = 306$ blocks). (a) $n_k = 20$ blocks; (b) $n_k = 150$ blocks.

Fig. 3 Comparison between predicted residual stiffness (Bayesian approach) and experimental results for specimen F312 ($S = 376.7$ MPa, $N = 306$ blocks). (a) $n_k = 20$ blocks; (b) $n_k = 150$ blocks.